

**DAMAGE TO THE DIGESTIVE TRACT IN COVID-19,
CAUSE OR CONSEQUENCE. WILL AN ORAL VACCINE BE EFFECTIVE?**

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Tikhonov D.G., Vladimirtsev V.A.

Annotation. Analysis of the pathways of the virus infiltration, the features of digestive lesions in COVID-19 and the search for an answer to the dilemma: Is the digestive system affected by this viral infection the cause or consequence? - allowed us to formulate a hypothesis about the possibility of developing a safe and effective oral vaccine against SARS-Cov-2. This paper substantiated the hypothesis. In our opinion, the oral vaccine against SARS-Cov-2 is likely to be the safest, even with the use of an attenuated strain of the virus.

Key words: SARS-Cov-2, COVID-19, digestive tract, oral vaccine

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We have formulated a scientific hypothesis that a certain part of the asymptomatic forms of COVID-19 cause SARS-Cov-2 to infiltrate the patient bypassing the airways, which allows to develop a safe and effective oral vaccine specific antigens of the new coronavirus (from 4.3% to 7.1% of the population according to population studies ([5] [4] q2) cannot be explained by the presence of cross-immunity on other strains of the coronavirus family, and a fairly high level of asymptomatic carriers of the virus (from 42.3% to 81% of the virus) with a high level of non-specific immunity among the population. There are several possible pathways to the new coronavirus, bypassing the airways: through the smirk and salivary glands and oral tract (defeat of the taste buds of the tongue) possibly the body's development of immunity. If so, the development of a safe oral vaccine will contribute to the successful prevention of the disease.

The Aim of this study is to substantiate the hypothesis that it is possible to develop a safe and effective oral vaccine against SARS-Cov-2 coronavirus infection.

Methods and materials. The review of scientific articles on the topic of research will be based on an analysis of scientific articles on COVID-19. Searches for articles relevant to our topic will be conducted in databases of Web of Sciences, Scopus, EBSCO, PubMed and eLIBRARY, as well as on links articles.

It should be noted that the fecal-oral pathway of transmission has not been confirmed until now, but even asymptomatic forms of the disease can form a stable immunity. The results of the study of patients stools for the detection of live viruses are contradictory. Probably, the virus is not adapted for survival in the gastrointestinal tract, but it is impossible to exclude this pathway of COVID infection. It should be noted that our hypothesis is supported by data published in peer-reviewed scientific publications. To confirm or refute the main provisions of the hypothesis, it is necessary to conduct experimental studies and clinical observations of patients with COVID-19.

What data in the press now support the provisions of the hypothesis put forward?:

1. Primary damage to the olfactory and taste receptors is a marker of a milder clinical variant of COVID-19. Thus, the violation of taste perception was found to be statistically significantly higher in patients who underwent outpatient than inpatient treatment, the same pattern was found in patients with olfactory disorders [7], [8].

2. In some patients, symptoms from the digestive system appear earlier and are the only manifestations of the disease in the absence of pulmonary symptoms [9],

[10]. It should be noted that symptoms of damage to the digestive system are equally common among the cohort of patients with mild and severe course. Analysis of the literature allows us to assume that the early appearance of symptoms of the digestive system more typical light variant clinical course of the disease, and the secondary connection for heavy (the body may be affected by a pathological process resulting in organ lesions of primary pulmonary focus). In a number of cases, symptoms of digestive disorders occur in up to 80% of cases. Based on this, the authors suggest two variants of a new coronavirus infection: "with pulmonary tropism" and "with gastrointestinal tropism" [11]. Some researchers assume that the intestinal epithelium may be the point of entry of the virus into the human body [12].

3. In the biopsies of the gastric mucosa, duodenum 12, and large intestine of a patient with COVID-19, abundant expression of the angiotensin-converting enzyme-2 (ACE-2) protein and the nucleocapsid protein of the virus was detected [13], which indicates that the digestive tract is almost the entire length of the gateway for virus entry into the body.

4. Experiments with the chimeric SARS Cov-2 virus showed that the virus in the simulated acidic stomach contents is inactivated within 10 minutes, the large intestine is reduced twice within an hour, and within 24 hours it is completely eliminated. The virus successfully replicated in the intestinal mucosa, while maintaining its virulence in the simulated content of hepatic bile and relatively satisfactorily in the small intestine. Attempts to isolate a live virus in the feces of patients were not successful, although in 1 gm of feces, about 105 – 107 copies of the RNA of the virus could be detected [14]. It should be noted that in gastric juice, high acidity is not kept constantly, but only during digestion, and in the inter-digestive period, the pH usually reaches 5-6. In addition, the gastric mucosa is covered with a thin layer of parietal mucus, under which neutral pH values are preserved. We found that among residents of regions with cold climates, there are reduced indicators of the acid-forming function of the gastric mucosa, which has adapted to produce active pepsin at low acidity values [15]. All these conditions in a number of individuals can contribute to the transit of SARS Cov-2 into the intestines, when it enters the stomach through the oral cavity. It should be noted that fluids can enter the 12-duodenum without lingering in the stomach.

Mass wearing of medical masks, after the emergence of the new coronavirus epidemic around the world, probably has a role in the emergence of a large number of asymptomatic forms of infection. So, in March, after

WHO declared the Cov-19 pandemic, a cruise ship left Argentina for a 21-day voyage. Only tourists were allowed on Board after a thorough check and temperature measurement. Several hand hygiene stations were set up in different locations on the ship. Everyone's temperature was measured daily. But on the 8th day of the voyage, one patient developed a fever. A strict isolation Protocol was put in place on the ship. All contacts between the crew and passengers were carried out in masks No. 95, and all passengers were given surgical masks, food was delivered three times a day to the cabin doors, but the ship was not processed. Argentina banned entry to its ports and the ship docked in Montevideo, Uruguay on the 13th day of the cruise. By that time, 21 people had symptoms of the coronavirus. Three had a high fever the next day. Uruguayan authorities have requested that all passengers and crew be tested for Cov-2 using reverse transcription PCR. Testing revealed 128 positive results out of 217 passengers and crew members. Out of 128 people with a positive result, only 24 people had symptoms, i.e. 104 were asymptomatic, or 81% of patients [3]. Wearing masks undoubtedly protects to some extent from the virus entering the respiratory tract, but it does not protect against contact infection. The main target for SARS Cov-2 is the lung. If the entrance gate of infection is the oral route, then the body probably has time to mobilize its defense mechanisms and the virus is quickly eliminated.

5. At the present time all over the world intensively developed vaccines against SARS Cov-2. The cheapest, safest and most convenient vaccine is undoubtedly the

oral vaccine, but, unfortunately, there are no studies in this direction in the world. The Cov-2 virus is well preserved in the contents of the small intestine, where it replicates intensively and causes an immune response, but is eliminated in the lumen of the large intestine [14]. These conditions are ideal for creating an oral vaccine.

In conclusion, it should be noted that it is likely that an oral vaccine against SARS-Cov-2 will be the safest, even if an attenuated strain of the virus is used. Currently, there are reliable ways to deliver the vaccine without its contact with the upper parts of the digestive tract and the acidic contents of the stomach. The probability of developing antibodies and other defense mechanisms when the vaccine is delivered to the lumen of the small intestine is high, but requires additional research.

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REFERENCES

1. Sood N. et al. Seroprevalence of SARS-CoV-2-Specific Antibodies Among Adults in Los Angeles County, California, on April 10-11, 2020. // *Jama*. 2020. Vol. 13. P. 98–99.
2. Zou J., Bretin A., Gewirtz A.T. Antibodies to SARS/CoV-2 in arbitrarily-selected Atlanta residents // *medRxiv*. 2020. Vol. 21, № 1. P. 1–12.
3. Ing A.J., Cocks C., Green J.P. COVID-19: in the footsteps of Ernest Shackleton // *Thorax*. 2020. P. 1–2.
4. Yang R., Gui X., Xiong Y. Comparison of Clinical Characteristics of Patients with Asymptomatic vs Symptomatic Coronavirus Disease 2019 in Wuhan, China. // *JAMA Netw. open*. 2020. Vol. 3, № 5. P. e2010182.
5. Colavita F. et al. SARS-CoV-2 Isolation From Ocular Secretions of a Patient With COVID-19 in Italy With Prolonged Viral RNA Detection // *Ann. Intern. Med.* Vol. 0, № 0. P. null.
6. To K.K.W. et al. Consistent detection of 2019 novel coronavirus in saliva // *Clin. Infect. Dis.* 2020. № Xx Xxxx. P. 4–6.
7. Lechien J.R. et al. Olfactory and gustatory dysfunctions as a clinical presentation of mild-to-moderate forms of the coronavirus disease (COVID-19): a multicenter European study // *Eur. Arch. Oto-Rhino-Laryngology*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2020. Vol. 2, № 0123456789.
8. Yan C.H. et al. Self-reported olfactory loss associates with outpatient clinical course in Covid-19 // *Int. Forum Allergy Rhinol.* 2020. P. 1–26.
9. Schmulson M., Dávalos M.F., Berumen J. Beware: Gastrointestinal symptoms can be a manifestation of COVID-19 // *Rev. Gastroenterol. Mex. Mexican Gastroenterology Association*, 2020. P. 0–5.
10. Cheung K.S. et al. Gastrointestinal Manifestations of SARS-CoV-2 Infection and Virus Load in Fecal Samples from the Hong Kong Cohort and Systematic Review and Meta-analysis // *Gastroenterology*. The American Gastroenterological Association, 2020.
11. Lo I.L. et al. Evaluation of SARS-CoV-2 RNA shedding in clinical specimens and clinical characteristics of 10 patients with COVID-19 in Macau // *Int. J. Biol. Sci.* 2020. Vol. 16, № 10. P. 1698–1707.
12. Zhang H. et al. Digestive system is a potential route of COVID-19: An analysis of single-cell coexpression pattern of key proteins in viral entry process // *Gut*. 2020. P. 1010–1018.
13. Xiao F. et al. Evidence for Gastrointestinal Infection of SARS-CoV-2 // *Gastroenterology*. Elsevier, Inc, 2020. Vol. 158, № 6. P. 1831-1833.e3.
14. Zang R. et al. TMPRSS2 and TMPRSS4 promote SARS-CoV-2 infection of human small intestinal enterocytes // *Sci. Immunol.* 2020. Vol. 5, № 47.
15. Tikhonov D. *Arkticheskaya meditsina [Arctic medicine]*. Yakutsk: YaSC SB RAS, 2010. 317 p. [In Russian].

Information about authors

1. **TIKHONOV Dmitry Gavrilievich**, MD, Professor, Senior Research Officer of the Scientific research Center of the medical Institute of the North-Eastern Federal University, 677009, Yakutsk, St. Bld. 8, Russia, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3385-9471>, e-mail: Tikhonov.dmitri@yandex.ru.

2. **VLADIMIRTSEV Vsevolod A.**, PhD. Free Researcher. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5480-3592>, e-mail: sevelot@mail.ru.